

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing

1 Year **EDGELESS!**

One year has swiftly passed since the start of the **EDGELESS** project, and what a year it has been!

It marks a year of remarkable progress and fruitful collaboration among our esteemed partners. Throughout this time, our consortium has diligently worked together, resulting in substantial achievements in research, stakeholder engagement, and raising public awareness about **EDGELESS's** activities.

Our Latest Highlights

EDGELESS Videos

This video tutorial introduces **EDGELESS**, showcasing how developers can deploy workflows on clusters of edge nodes within orchestration domains. It demonstrates the creation of a dual-channel function in Rust.

This video demonstrates how to create a workflow. It covers the generation of numeric values using a sensor simulator, filtering these values within a specified range, computing averages, and transmitting results to a Redis server. This showcases the interaction between functions and resources within **EDGELESS's** runtime environment.

Visit **EDGELESS** YouTube Channel

EDGELESS Blogs!

We have been blogging since the beginning of our project and so far it has led to very interesting discussions! We are happy to have an open dialogue with everyone interested in and/or influenced by EDGELESS and consider the thoughts you share.

See our latest blogs below:

Serverless computing: a security perspective

In serverless computing, the application logic is decomposed into a series of small, ephemeral, and stateless functions, each operating within its own isolated execution environment, such as a container.

Boosting efficient orchestration in EDGELESS using AI

The brain is the main organ with computational capabilities, containing information that allow humans to remember, reason and take action. That's because the majority of neurons belong to the central nervous system, but not all of them.

Upcoming Events

SEATED

1st Workshop on Serverless at the Edge

EDGELESS will organise the workshop **SEATED** on Serverless at the Edge co-located with ACM HPDC to be hosted in Pisa next June.

While serverless computing and FaaS have emerged as the dominant choice for mobile applications, their transformative potential within the context of edge-native applications, e.g., in the Internet of Things, remains largely unexplored. The objective of **SEATED** is to bridge this gap by investigating how the edge, possibly in combination with the cloud, can unlock new opportunities for serverless/FaaS in distributed applications and services, which often possess unique requirements and structural differences.

SEATED aims to build a scientific-oriented forum for research and industrial communities to present and discuss their latest results, ongoing work, and emerging research directions regarding serverless at the edge. Managing edge resources for high-performance, scientific, and general-purpose serverless applications is an open research field, which covers many aspects of distributed systems, including computing, state and data management, workflow management, and resource orchestration. Furthermore, complex serverless applications require top-notch hardware accelerators, emerging virtualization, and enhanced security.

CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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